

IMPRESSIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES WITH INDOCTRINATING RESEARCH-BASED TO CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS FOR EDUCATIONAL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

To design the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs) to their creative thinking skills in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University, and to monitor and evaluate students' learning outcomes of the determinants and effects of the RBLs which learning strategies enhancing educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills. Administration consisted of 38 junior educational students in faculty of education with the purposive random sampling technique with composed of the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), and the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS). Statistically significant was analyzed, and junior educational students were responded of their QSC and CTT which indicated that the scale means showed off 2.56 on the instructional content for enhancing educational students' creative thinking skills, and standard deviation for the QSC on the developing instructional model indicated of 0.71. The finding also further supported students' need has indicated that their performances were enhanced to their creative thinking abilities evident of high level. Junior educational students were impressed of their indoctrinating RBLs to their creative thinking skills that it has revealed their mean scores of the QSS were high level, suitability. Students' learning achievements with the DIM, the average mean scores were found evidence of 26.21, it means as 81% of the variance in students' creative thinking skills to their instructional management with the RBLs class was attributable to their indoctrination of their CTT

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and showed the statistically significant between students' outcomes of their post and pre- test at the level of 0.01, differently. The instructional efficiency value of the RBLS was assessed with the E_1/E_2 and indicated of 80.73/80.98, and the average mean score and standard deviation of students' responses to their QSS revealed of high level as 4.26, and 0.46, consequently.

Keywords: designing instructional model, educational students, indoctrination, research-based, leaning strategies, creative thinking skills

1. Introduction

In the two last decades of information, students will have to take more and more responsibility for their own learning processes, which are initiated and controlled by realistic, job-oriented or competency-oriented learning tasks. These changes are referred to as the "new learning" (Simons et al., 2000). The implementation of this type of curricular change into new learning practices will affect teachers' role perceptions. Teachers will have to change their role from being "transmitters of content" too becoming "coaches of students' learning processes" (Pratt et al., 1998; Vermunt and Verloop, 1999). From this viewpoint, teacher trainers' problems of curriculum innovation can be interpreted as problems of instructional design (Enkenberg, 2001). In addition, the increasing emphasis on real life problem solving tasks requires teachers to develop complex design skills. Teachers' participation in the curriculum redesign process is considered to be a crucial factor in the success of curriculum innovation. Instructional design models help instructional designers to make sense of abstract learning theory and enable real world application. An instructional design model provides structure and meaning to an instructional design problem. Many of them have common instructional design principles and patterns, the most common instructional design models that are used to design learning experiences, courses, and instructional content.

Design is more than a process, that process, and resulting product, represent a framework of thinking (Driscoll & Carliner, 2005: 9). Usually, an *instructional design model* tells how to organize appropriate pedagogical scenarios to achieve instructional goals. In more abstract terms an *instructional design model* is a kind of abstract design rule for a given instructional design approach or a given pedagogic strategy. Instructional models are guidelines or sets of strategies on which the approaches to teaching by instructors are based. Effective instructional models are based on learning theories. Learning theories describe the ways that theories believe people learn new ideas and concepts. Often, they explain the relationship between

information of their knowledge and information of their trying to learn (Braxton, Bronico, & Looms, 1995).

Instruction, even when designed and based on sound instructional principles, oftentimes does not stimulate learners' motivation to learn. The result may be that learners may not be motivated to pursue lifelong learning and use the knowledge and skills learned to deliver patient care (Gustafson & Branch, 1997). This study was integrated the *Instructional Design for Teaching and Learning* specialization to design for preparing the expert practitioners to design, deliver, and evaluate the educational learning programs on the *Educational Foundation Subject* for the junior educational students as well as the standardizations' framework of the curriculum of Bachelor of Education Programs, Faculty of Education, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat Rajabhat is personalized content which it followed as the Secretariat of the Teachers Council of Thailand onto published in the Royal Thai Government Gazette in the quality of graduate educational students who are trainees students and must be training professional learning participation on school practices, and teaching internship I and II in the two semesters in the schools in the senior level.

Impressive is the making or tending to make a marked impression, having the power to excite attention, awe, or admiration (an impressive display of skill) that it means having the power to produce deep emotion. Impressive implies compelling attention, wonder, or conviction (an impressive list of achievements) (Collins English Dictionary, 2012). Focused on impressive students are having the power to impress the mind or feelings especially in a positive way (an impressive speech). In this research study, the impressive students are having the ability to impress the mind; arousing admiration, awe, respect, moving, admirable, an impressive ceremony of the junior educational students.

Indoctrination, or thought reform, is the process of forcible inculcating, ideas, attitudes, cognitive strategies or a professional methodology by coercion (Funk and Wagnalls, 1972). Conspiring institutions such as police and mental hospitals have been widely used as a *modus operandi* of indoctrinators. Some distinguish indoctrination from education. Claiming that the indoctrinated person is expected not to question or critically examine the doctrine they have taught (Wilson, 1964). As such the term may be used pejoratively or as a buzz word, often in the context of political opinions, theory, religious dogma or anti-religious convictions. The term is closely linked to socialization; however, in common discourse, *indoctrination* is sometimes associated with negative connotations, while *socialization* refers to cultural or educational learning. In this research study, designing the religious indoctrination, the original sense of *indoctrination*, refers to a process of imparting doctrine in an authoritative way to strategy of junior educational students who are able to imply forcibly or coercively

causing them to act and think on the basis of a certain ideology of junior educational students to their educational foundation classes.

What is Research-Based and Who decides? In a climate of increased accountability, schools, educational institutes, universities and districts are pushed to demonstrate that they are employing research-based strategies to improve instruction. But what makes a teaching strategy, technique, or practice “research-based”? “Research-based” is finding what works for which students under what circumstances and determining how it can be replicated (LessonCast, 2011). In terms of learning strategies, which help students organize their thinking and be successful learners. Sounds simple, but there's a little more to it than following a recipe for instruction, and read on to learn about important research and how this directs instructional practices (Linde, 2012).

What Are Learning Strategies? In education, research team defines learning strategies as techniques used by students to become familiar with information. In other words, it's how research team takes in information and apply it to other areas of our lives. Without good strategies, students can struggle with acquiring and using the information they are taught in the classroom. Luckily, educators can directly instruct students on how to become active learners by teaching learning strategies, those strategies that show students how to take in new information and use it in valuable ways.

Why Research-Based? Research team composed of educational teachers brings a lot of instinct to their classrooms, but they aren't born knowing what is best for all students. Educational research helps illuminate what has been shown to be effective so teachers can use the best methods of instruction in their own classes. Research can be broken down into two categories: brain science and teachers. Research team may have heard the words 'cognitive research' when determining student needs or preparing professional papers. Brain science, also known as cognitive science, is the area of research that looks into the brain, sometimes literally, to help us understand how it works. The information gleaned from cognitive research steers instructional methods. Separate from cognitive science is research based on the experience of teachers. Doctoral teachers are a great source of educational research. The depth of their experience in the classroom provides researchers with valuable information about how students act and react to instructional methods and content.

How students learn? Educational research shines the light on how children learn. There are three viewpoints that can help determine whether a student is using learning strategies or not. The first learning strategy asks the question, '*How do you remember new information?*' There are a range of tools used by active learners that help them retain information that is new to them. *How do you study information?* Once information has been initially stored in the brain, active learners utilize a separate set of techniques that

help push the surface knowledge to long-term memory. And finally, the third strategy to active learning asks, *'What do you do with your new learning?'* Successful students don't just take in new learning; they use it in expressive ways like (Linde, 2012). In this research study, doctoral teachers are able to encourage junior educational students to incorporate active learning principles into their own studies by assigning some of these tools in class. For instance, as students begin to learn about the Educational Foundation Subject, they might start the unit by not only memorizing facts and dates pertinent to the educational system, but also rephrasing the information into their own practicing, training, and visualizing its.

Focusing on creativity, it is a phenomenon whereby something new and somehow valuable is formed. The created item may be intangible (such as an idea, a scientific theory, a musical composition, or a joke) or a physical object (such as an invention, a literary work, or a painting), covering the relations between creativity and general intelligence, mental and neurological processes, personality type and creative ability, creativity and mental health; the potential for fostering creativity through education and training, especially as augmented by technology; and the application of creative resources to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning (Mumford, 2003). Creative thinking is actually both capacity to blend or synthesize to present suggestions, images, or experience in unique ways and the expertise of thinking, responding and dealing in a creative way characterized by a higher level of development, risk taking and divergent thinking. Since creative thinking is fostered within greater education, should be recognized from less concentrated forms of creativeness such as, the creativity displayed by a small child's sketching, which stems not really through an understanding of contacts, however from an ignorance of the limitations (EDU Resource, 2014).

The main research study for improving junior educational students on their creative thinking skills, using the seven creative thinking skills, seven demonstrated during the call are ones which benefit both those who display them and those working with them too; suspending advocacy of research team's own idea to push for educational student's concept, putting research team's own idea to the same test research team apply to an idea from educational student's else, combining two different ideas and making them better (not muddled) as one idea, letting educational student's else take "ownership" of research team's idea in order to build support for it, displaying the patience to wait for educational student else to say what needs to be said so all research team has to do is agree, sticking to research team guns amid challenges to a creative idea which makes solid strategic sense, and always looking for new creative skills to develop in themselves and those around research team. Not only does research team want to make themselves stronger creatively at every juncture, it's in research team best interests to help improve the creative performance of students overall team.

Creative meetings are a great opportunity to spot gaps others labor under as well as seeing students own creative shortcomings. Inventory what research team saw (or didn't see) after a creative meeting and get to work filling the gaps of educational students were assessed.

In terms of the context of Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University; founded in 1973, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University is a non-profit public higher education institution located in the medium-sized town of Kamphaeng Phet (population range of 10,000-49,999 inhabitants). Officially accredited/recognized by the Ministry of Education, Thailand, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University (KPRU) is a coeducational higher education institution. Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University (KPRU) offers courses and programs leading to officially recognized higher education degrees in several areas of study. KPRU also provides several academic and non-academic facilities and services to students including a library, as well as administrative services.

The oldest faculty at Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University, the Faculty of Education began its operation with the establishment of the College of Teacher Education, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat. The college's main goal was to produce teachers with a higher degree. Its full status as a faculty was granted when the college became a branch campus of the Institute of Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat which later became an independent institution as Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. The faculty has continued its responsibility to produce teachers and educators with expertise in various fields for the development of education at both local and national levels. In addition to offering degree programs at both undergraduate and post-graduate levels, the faculty also emphasizes research for the development of education, as well as the provision of academic services to work units and people in local communities.

2. Methodology

This research study is to design on the instructional strategies for presenting content describe the ways of presenting information to teaching and learning on a group of educational foundation classroom environment to design the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs) to their creative thinking skills at the faculty of education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University, and to monitor and evaluate junior educational students' learning outcomes of the determinants and effects of the RBLs which learning strategies help educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills and be successful learners were designed. *These two decisions yield four basic research designs; a preliminary quantitative methods study with the questionnaire technique was used. The conclusions consider further research designs and the expertise necessary for multiple-methods research.*

2.1 Research Procedure

Using the Action Research Technique was designed on the instructional strategies for presenting content describe the ways of presenting information to teaching and learning on a group of educational foundation classroom environment to the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs) to their creative thinking skills at the faculty of education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. The research team would be described a framework for designing learning educational foundation subject class environment to include two templates that aids in the instructional design. The research procedure was eight main steps that followed as:

Step I: To Build up and Analyze of the Research Instrumental Qualities

It was considered important to discover what the quantitative methods, such as; questionnaire, testing documents, and the instructional model, such as; the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS), and the *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs). Most of these research instruments were checked and analyzed with the five expert professional educators are valid and reliable for use in this further of this research study.

Step II: To Analyze the Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLs)

Using the IOC value (Index of item Objective Congruence) was measured the validity of the Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLs) which revealed evidence higher of 0.60, significantly.

Step III: Research Instruments were Tried Out

Using the target group which was consisted of 34 junior educational students who sat the other group to analyze of the research instruments; the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS), and the *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs) were tried out.

Step IV: To Analyze the Content Validity

Using the IOC (Index of Item Objective Congruence) was analyzed the validity of the research instrumental content validity, the IOC indicated that of higher than 0.60

Step V: Validity and Reliability

The internal consistency reliability of the version QSC, DIM, and QSS used in this study were determined by calculating Cronbach alpha coefficient for the items of these research instruments using educational foundation environmental climates' perceptions

scores. The internal consistency was analyzed of the QSC, DIM, and QSS, which indicated that evidence of 0.89, 0.76, and 0.89, consequently.

Step VI: Synthesis of Foundational Theory Thinking of Instructional Model

To specify of the foundational theory the developing instructional model through disciple and effect which composed of 8 factors, such as; background and introduction, relative thinking and theory, instructional purposes, instructional processes, teachers' roles, learners' roles, media and learning source, and evaluation factors.

Step VII: Inventive the RBLS Instructional Model

To invent and analyze the *Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLS)* was checked the instructional significant with the five professional educators were determined by measuring this model and their responses of the quality model indicated that evidence of high level ($\bar{X} = 4.28$, S.D. = 0.12) was satisfied.

2.3 Research Objectives

1. To develop for designing the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLS)* to their creative thinking skills at the faculty of education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University.
2. To monitor and evaluate students' learning outcomes of the determinants and effects of the RBLS which learning strategies enhanced the educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills and be successful learners were designed.

2.4 Research Instruments

1. The Indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLS)*
2. The *Questionnaire on Strategized Context (QSC)*
3. The *Developing Instructional Model (DIM)*
4. The *Critical Thinking Test (CTT)*
5. The *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction (QSS)*.

2.5 Sample

To administer with the sample size which consisted of 38 junior educational students who sat at the Faculty of Education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. Using the purposive random sampling was selected.

2.6 Data Analysis

A. Using the foundational Statistics; such as; Percentage, Mean, Average mean score, standard deviation to analysis of the data to measure Educational Foundation Subject classroom junior students' perceptions of both the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), and the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS) which were assessed the research instruments with the internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha Reliability) coefficients for the sample in this present study as indices of scale reliability and validity.

B. The overall aims of this study was to describe the determinants and effects of students' perceptions of Educational Foundation Subject classroom environment of the RBLS which learning strategies help educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills and be successful learners were designed. Using the *Index of Item-Objective Congruence* (IOC) was measured the limited to the assessment of unidimensional items or items that measure specified composites of skills. In modern test development, items are sometimes developed to be multidimensional assessments or measures of multiple combinations of skills.

3. Results

This research study was to design the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLS) to their creative thinking skills at the faculty of education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. The monitoring and evaluations of students' learning outcomes to their determinants and effects with learning strategies of the RBLS Model to help junior educational students' organizations toward their indoctrinating creative thinking skills were assessed. Administrations of the target groups were consisted of 38 junior educational students in Faculty of Education with the purposive random sampling technique. In these results, appropriate statistical procedures were used, in order to validate the questionnaires. The procedures included *Index of Item-Objective Congruence* (IOC), percentage, average mean scores, Cronbach alpha. The four instruments, namely; the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), and the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS) are valid and reliable for further use in this research study.

A. The Instructional Model through Impressive Educational Students of their Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLS) to their Creative Thinking Skills

A summary of statistical information currently available for the four research instruments was considered previously and included information about each scale

between the perceptions of junior educational students in Educational Foundation Subject classroom environment. Table 1 is illustrated using the context property and students' needs of their instructional management in their class.

Table 1: Average Mean Scores and Standard Deviation for the Context Property and Students' Needs

Questioning Subjects	Property Context		Students' Needs	
	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.
Leaning Substances/Learning Skill Scale				
1. To get knowledge on creative thinking ability	2.44	0.71	4.39	0.50
2. To opportune content for fostering creative thinking ability	2.15	0.85	4.23	0.62
3. To investigate of the multisource learning	3.05	0.60	4.37	0.47
4. To understand on creative thinking ability processes clearly	2.44	0.71	4.22	0.51
5. To understand developing the creative thinking ability steps	2.54	0.68	4.29	0.65
6. To have the learning methods for enhancing creative thinking ability	2.37	0.70	4.33	0.69
7. To develop creative thinking	2.15	0.85	4.03	0.79
8. To develop learning process for enhancing develop creative thinking	2.05	0.60	4.37	0.47
<i>Average Mean Scores</i>	2.45	0.73	4.26	0.59
Activity/Learning Experience Scale				
9. To cooperate and relative with other learners and instructor <i>ได้เรียนรู้</i>	3.09	0.53	3.88	0.50
10. To emphasis learning activities of content and training creative thinking	3.05	0.60	3.96	0.58
11. To be informed learning purposes	2.47	0.56	4.26	0.67
12. To manage learning activities for enhancing and developing creative thinking processes	2.15	0.85	4.03	0.79
13. To set problem learning activities for students' solving problems	2.15	0.85	4.03	0.79
14. To opportune learners' activities of their synthesis solving problems	3.05	0.60	3.96	0.58
15. To opportune learners' individualized training with their groups	2.93	0.47	3.96	0.58
16. To use the multiple activities for fostering creative thinking abilities of learners	2.37	0.65	4.26	0.67
17. To opportune of learners' self-presentation and presenting sub-group	2.09	0.78	4.03	0.79
18. To opportune of learners' discussion with their instructor and other learners	3.05	0.60	3.96	0.58
19. To get idea on learners' self-evaluation <i>ให้ผู้เรียนได้ประเมินผลการคิดของตนเอง</i>	2.44	0.71	4.26	0.67
20. To evaluate learners with their participating activities and learner thinking processes	2.15	0.85	4.03	0.79
<i>Average Mean Scores Scale</i>	2.68	0.68	4.05	0.65
Instructional Management on Today Scale				
21. To design on lecture instruction	2.41	0.65	4.26	0.67
22. To design on descriptive instruction	3.52	0.56	3.37	0.58

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Questioning Subjects	Property Context		Students' Needs	
	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	$\bar{X}$	S.D.
23. To design on emphasizing research instruction	3.59	0.40	3.40	0.49
24. To opportune on participating commendation by learner	2.70	0.66	4.26	0.65
25. To manage on self-thinking and participating other learners with their group discussion	3.05	0.60	3.96	0.58
26. To manage on data training subjective	2.44	0.71	4.26	0.67
27. To manage on selected data to relate solving problem activities	2.15	0.85	4.03	0.79
28. To manage on searched for truly data from other sourcing activities	2.57	0.76	4.30	0.74
29. To manage on individualized digesting data between truly conception and misconception data activities	2.70	0.66	4.26	0.65
30. To manage on solving problem from questioning subject or situation	2.33	0.64	4.26	0.67
<i>Average Mean Scores</i>	2.52	0.73	4.20	0.70
Total Average Mean Scores	2.56	0.71	4.16	0.65

The scale means ranged from 2.05 to 3.05 on the *Leaning Substances/Learning Skill* scale, ranged from 2.09 to 3.09 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 2.15 to 3.59 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale. Standard deviations for the *Leaning Substances/Learning Skill* scale ranged from 0.60 to 0.85, ranged from 0.53 to 0.85 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 2.15 to 3.59, and ranged from 0.40 to 0.85 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale; and total average mean score evidence of 2.56 and standard deviation value of 0.71 on students' responses from the Context Property. In terms of the students' responses of their needs; the scale means ranged from 4.03 to 4.29 on the *Leaning Substances/Learning Skill* scale, ranged from 3.88 to 4.36 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 4.26 to 4.30 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale. Standard deviations for the *Leaning Substances/Learning Skill* scale ranged from 0.47 to 0.79, ranged from 0.53 to 0.85 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 0.50 to 0.79, and ranged from 0.49 to 0.79 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale; and total average mean score evidence of 4.16 and standard deviation value of 0.65. Table 1 reveals that differences between students' perceptions of their context property and their needs for all the three scales of the Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLS) model.

B. Designing the Instructional Model through Impressive Educational Students with the Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies to their Creative Thinking Skills

The assessing results of the designing the instructional model through impressive educational students with the indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies Model* (RBLs) to their creative thinking skills. In most case, Table 2 presents assessing students' responses of their suitability in terms of means and standard deviation for the indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies Model* to their creative thinking skills.

In Table 2, the finding also further supports relative research in this study has indicated that students' responses of their suitability in terms of means and standard deviation for the indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies Model* to their creative thinking skills perceive to be present a more desirable educational foundation subject classroom environment was created ($\bar{X} = 4.28$, S.D.= 0.12).

Table 2: Means and Standard Deviation for the Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies to their Creative Thinking Skills

RBLs Model	Mean scores		Suitability level
	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	
1. Background and inductive developing indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.20	0.84	High
2. Foundational theory thinking of the developing indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.40	0.55	High
3. To set off the aims for developing the indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.00	0.71	High
4. To define the meaning for developing the indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.20	0.84	High
5. To set off the factors for developing the indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.00	0.71	High
6. To explain of the instructional designs for developing the indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills on three topics	4.20	0.84	
6.1 Pre-experience approach			
6.1.1 Meaning	4.60	0.89	Highest
6.1.2 Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.20	0.45	High
6.2 The five experiencing approach			
6.2.1 To set off problem			
1) Definition	4.40	0.89	High
2) Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.20	0.84	High
6.2.2 To set off the solving problem method			
1) Definition	4.20	0.84	High
2) Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.40	0.89	High
6.2.3 Selected data approach			
1) Definition	4.60	0.89	Highest

RBLs Model	Mean scores		Suitability level
	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	
1. Background and inductive developing indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.20	0.84	High
2) Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.40	0.89	High
6.2.4 Data analysis approach			
1) Definition	4.20	0.84	High
2) Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.40	0.89	High
6.2.5 Concluding approach			
1) Definition	4.00	0.71	High
2) Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.20	0.84	High
6.3 Later experiencing approach			
6.3.1 Definition	4.20	0.84	High
6.3.2 Thinking and foundational theory concordance	4.40	0.89	High
7. To set off the instructional BBLs model for developing the indoctrination of the RBLs Model for learner's creative thinking skills	4.20	0.84	High
8. To set off the determinants and effects of the instructional RBLs model for developing the indoctrination of learner's creative thinking skills			High
9. To set off the instructor's activating roles of the instructional RBLs model for developing the indoctrination of learner's creative thinking skills	4.00	0.71	High
10. To set off the learner's activating roles of the instructional RBLs model for developing the indoctrination of learner's creative thinking skills	4.20	0.84	High
11. To set off the using adoptions of the instructional RBLs model for developing the indoctrination of learner's creative thinking skills	4.60	0.89	High
Average mean scores	4.28	0.12	High

C. Assessing Students' Responses of their Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies to their Creative Thinking Skills with the Index of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC)

The quality of information obtained from the administration of a measurement instrument is assessed using evidence provided from a set of common test theory procedures for developing the indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategy Model* instrument. To appropriately use and interpret data obtained from a measurement instrument, there must be operational definitions of the constructs being measured and information on the reliability and validity of the scores. The index of item-objective congruence is a procedure used in test development for evaluating content validity at the item development stage. In Table 3, reveals of the mean scores, standard deviation, and scoring percentage of the efficiency value of formative processing assessment (E₁) and the efficiency value of summative resulting assessment (E₂).

Table 3: Means and Standard Deviation for the Indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies to their Creative Thinking Skills with the Index of Item-Objective Congruence (IOC)

Efficiency value of the RBLs	Total scores	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	Scoring Percentage
Efficiency value of formative processing assessment (E ₁)	3420	72.66	1.26	80.73
Efficiency value of summative resulting assessment (E ₂)	1140	26.21	1.12	80.98
IOC value (E ₁ /E ₂)	84.07/83.85			

The adjusted measure assesses congruence between an efficiency value of formative processing assessment (E₁) and the efficiency value of summative resulting assessment (E₂) and an identified set of objectives. A second set of output for the IOC value (E₁/E₂) measuring multiple objectives is provided as for comparing interpretations made using the adjusted measure. This output also consists of the scoring percentages, the index value for the valid objective, and the average ratings of the experts on each objective that evidence of 84.07/83.85.

D. Assessing Students' Perceptions of their Satisfactory for the the Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction (QSS)

Educational foundation learning environment has been defined as everything that is happening in the classroom in the department of curriculum and instruction, faculty of education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. In Table 4, the results of this study have shown that the educational environment affects junior educational students' achievement, happiness, motivation, and success to their satisfactory for the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction (QSS)* was assessed.

Table 4: Means and Standard Deviation for Assessing Students' Perceptions of their Satisfactory with the QSS

Questioning Items for Students' Perceptions	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	Evidence value level
<i>Learning Activity Scale</i>			
1. Learning with this model that make scene to self-control and accepting charity rules with learning others	4.39	0.58	High
2. Learning with this model, which it has been built up of enhancement and decision on developing analysis thinking	4.26	0.54	High
3. Learning with this model, which learner considers training thinking process to get ideas for understanding effects of improving learning achievement	4.17	0.49	High
4. Learning with this model, which learner gets opportunity of learner's thinking and training reasons	4.56	0.59	High
<i>Average mean scores</i>	4.35	0.55	High
<i>Classroom Learning Environment Scale</i>			
5. Learner is too fun and friendly with instructor can depend on build up in	4.34	0.40	High

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classroom environment			
6. Learner is good related in this class with other friends and instructor	4.52	0.59	High
7. Learner is able to have interactive between sub group and other groups to create idea ranges	4.27	0.68	High
Average mean scores	4.38	0.44	High
Proportional Benefit Scale			
8. Learner understands on research methodology processes	3.89	0.58	High
9. Learner is developed creative skills to their analysis thinking ability	4.22	0.50	High
10. Learner is charitable to apply the learning knowledge of the practicing and able to use for daily life	4.09	0.59	High
Average mean scores	4.07	0.54	High
Total average mean scores	4.26	0.49	High

Table 4 reports the mean of the learner satisfied average mean scores in the three scales was 2.26 and standard deviation of 0.49 at the evidence of high level, which was considered to be positive of their instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating RBLs to their creative thinking skills for monitoring and evaluating students' learning outcomes of the determinants and effects of the RBLs which learning strategies help educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills were designed, respectively.

4. Conclusions

In this research study was to develop an *instructional design model* is a kind of design rule for a given instructional design approach or a given pedagogic strategy. Instructional models are guidelines or sets of strategies on which the approaches to teaching by instructors are based. Effective instructional models are based on learning theories. This study was integrated the *Instructional Design for Teaching and Learning* specialization to design for preparing the expert practitioners to design, deliver, and evaluate the educational learning programs on the *Educational Foundation Subject* for the junior educational students as well as the standardizations' framework of the curriculum of Bachelor of Education Programs, Faculty of Education, Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat Rajabhat is personalized content which it followed as the Secretariat of the Teachers Council of Thailand onto published in the Royal Thai Government Gazette in the quality of graduate educational students. In this research study, designing the religious indoctrination, the original sense of indoctrination, refers to a process of imparting doctrine in an authoritative way to strategy of junior educational students to act and think on the basis of a certain ideology of junior educational students to their educational foundation classes for improving their creative thinking skills.

The research procedure was eight main steps that followed as; to design on the instructional strategies for presenting content describe the ways of presenting information to teaching and learning on a group of educational foundation classroom environment to design the instructional model through impressive educational students of their indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs) to their creative thinking skills; to build up and analyze of the research instrumental qualities, to analyze the RBLs Model, research instruments were tried out, to analyze the content validity, validity and reliability, synthesis of foundational theory thinking of instructional model, and inventive the RBLs instructional model.

Using the research instruments, namely; The Indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* (RBLs), the *Questionnaire on Strategized Context* (QSC), the *Developing Instructional Model* (DIM), the *Critical Thinking Test* (CTT), and the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction* (QSS) with the sample size which consisted of 38 junior educational students who sat at the Faculty of Education in Kamphaeng Phet Rajabhat University. Using the purposive random sampling was selected. Assessing research instruments with the *Index of Item-Objective Congruence* (IOC) and the foundational statistics to analysis of the data to measure junior students' perceptions with the internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha Reliability) coefficients as indices of scale reliability and validity.

In terms of the students' responses of their needs; the scale means ranged from 4.03 to 4.29 on the *Learning Substances/Learning Skill* scale, ranged from 3.88 to 4.36 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 4.26 to 4.30 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale. Standard deviations for the *Learning Substances/Learning Skill* scale ranged from 0.47 to 0.79, ranged from 0.53 to 0.85 for the *Activity/Learning Experience* scale, and ranged from 0.50 to 0.79, and ranged from 0.49 to 0.79 for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale for the *Instructional Management on Today* scale; and total average mean score evidence of 4.16 and standard deviation value of 0.65. The finding also further supports relative research in this study has indicated that students' responses of their suitability in terms of means and standard deviation for the indoctrinating *Research-Based Learning Strategies* Model to their creative thinking skills perceive to be present a more desirable educational foundation subject classroom environment was created. The IOC value (E_1/E_2) for the valid objective, and the average ratings of the experts on each objective that evidence of 84.07/83.85.

5. Discussions

This study is significant for three reasons. First, it is likely to provide information for explaining the junior educational students' high average mean scores on educational foundation subject later their learning outcomes of their RBLs which learning strategies

help educational students organize of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills and be successful learners were designed. Second, this study is likely to improve teacher-student relationships in Educational Foundation Subject classroom environment in developed and organized junior educational students of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills to improve student outcomes. Third, the study is likely contribute to learning strategies of their indoctrinating creative thinking skills and their responses of the satisfaction to their development the instructional model toward their creative thinking skills that evidence of high level were assessed with the *Developing Instructional Model (DIM)*, the *Critical Thinking Test (CTT)*, and the *Questionnaire on Student Satisfaction (QSS)*, significantly.

Designing the instructional model through impressive educational students is an instructional design model that has the goal of producing more effective teaching and learning for the indoctrinating Research-Based Learning Strategies (RBLs) is an acronym that stands for the various steps in the model to their creative thinking skills. The RBLs process is really just a matter of common sense. However, it is good to follow a regimented guide to improve instructor teaching technique. Any effective instructor knows that the perfection of their technique does not come overnight, and there is always educational foundation classroom learning environment for improvement. By following the RBLs process, instructor will be sure to improve instructor teaching for educational foundation subject in academic years to come up, interestingly.

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